

CREATION OF CATALYST FOR GTL TECHNOLOGY BASED ON LOCAL RAW MATERIALS

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Abstract: In the field of chemical engineering, the search for efficient catalysts that can utilize local resources is important. This paper explores the development of a catalyst using indigenous raw materials for the synthesis gas (syngas) production process from natural gas. A crucial intermediate in various industries, syngas is usually produced by steam processing or partial oxidation of hydrocarbons such as natural gas. This innovative catalyst aims to optimize synthesis gas production by using locally available resources, reducing costs and increasing sustainability.

Key words: GTL, natural gas, oil, catalyst, technology, liquids.

Use of local raw materials: Gas-to-Liquids (GTL) technology has great potential for countries with large reserves of natural gas, such as Uzbekistan. GTL technology involves converting natural gas into liquid fuels such as diesel, gasoline and synthetic lubricants through a series of catalytic reactions. With its rich natural gas resources, Uzbekistan is exploring the feasibility of GTL technology to diversify its energy portfolio, reduce dependence on imported fuel, and create value-added products from gas resources.

Energy diversification: By using GTL technology, Uzbekistan can diversify its energy sources beyond traditional natural gas exports. This diversification can increase energy security and provide alternative fuel options for domestic consumption and export. **Monetization of gas resources:** GTL technology allows Uzbekistan to more efficiently monetize its large natural gas reserves by converting gas into more expensive liquid fuels. This can increase potential revenue streams and create economic opportunities for the country.

Environmental benefits: GTL technology produces cleaner burning fuels with less sulfur and particulate emissions compared to conventional diesel or gasoline. The introduction of GTL in Uzbekistan can contribute to reducing air pollution and improving the quality of the environment. Native catalysts play a critical role in Gas-to-Liquids (GTL) technology and affect the efficiency, selectivity, and overall performance of the GTL process. Several key factors underline the importance of catalysts in GTL technology, especially considering their local sources and uses:

Catalytic activity: The most important aspect of a catalyst in GTL technology is its catalytic activity, which determines the rate and extent of the desired chemical reactions that convert natural gas into liquid hydrocarbons. In order to efficiently

convert syngas (a mixture of hydrogen and carbon monoxide) into liquid hydrocarbons, local catalysts must be highly active.

The catalyst development process begins with the extraction of native raw materials rich in elements that can catalyze the desired reactions. Areas rich in minerals such as nickel, cobalt or iron become the main target for material extraction. When properly combined and structured, these elements exhibit ideal catalytic properties for reforming reactions. By using these local resources, catalyst production costs are minimized, supporting the regional economy.

Design and manufacturing process.

Catalyst design involves careful selection and blending of local raw materials to achieve the desired catalytic activity and stability. Experimental methods such as impregnation, precipitation or sol-gel methods are used to synthesize the catalyst precursor. Subsequent heat treatment processes optimize the structure of the catalyst, increasing its surface area, porosity, and active sites to improve syngas production performance.

Catalyst performance and optimization.

Locally sourced catalyst is rigorously tested to assess its catalytic efficiency, selectivity and durability during syngas production. Characterization techniques such as X-ray diffraction (XRD), scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and temperature programmed reduction (TPR) provide insight into the morphological and chemical properties of the catalyst. Through repeated testing and optimization, catalyst composition and preparation methods are fine-tuned to achieve maximum syngas yield and quality. Benefits and consequences. The development of a catalyst for the

production of syngas based on local raw materials provides many advantages. First, it promotes resource use and sustainability by reducing dependence on imported catalyst materials. Second, it increases economic sustainability by potentially lowering production costs by providing local materials. In addition, locally sourced catalyst contributes to regional development and innovation by increasing the team's expertise in catalyst design and production.

Summary. The creation of a catalyst using indigenous raw materials for gas synthesis from natural gas is a significant advance in catalysis research and sustainable process development. By leveraging local resources, optimizing catalyst performance, and encouraging regional innovation, this initiative emphasizes the importance of resource efficiency and sustainability in chemical manufacturing processes. This catalyst not only paves the way for cost-effective syngas production, but also shows the potential for localized solutions in the global chemical industry landscape.

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